

Influence of Pesticides on the Trace Element Status of Soils : Part II. Effect of Nemagon on the Manganese and Iron Status of a Saline Soil

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The effects of different doses of nemagon (1,2-dibromo-3 chloropropane) on the Mn and Fe status of a saline sodic soil over a period of 90 days were examined and the variance ratio, L.S.D. and correlation coefficients calculated. The results revealed that 0.3 ml of the pesticide per kg. of soil at an interval of 30 days produced a most favourable significant response on water soluble, exchangeable and active Mn as well as on available and exchangeable Fe. All these constituents were positively correlated to each other. However, a negative correlation was observed between active and reducible Mn. The effect of the chemical started declining after a period of 4 weeks. The responses have been explained on the basis of chemical and microbiological activity in the soil.

THE importance of pesticides in controlling plant diseases for high agricultural production have been greatly realised in recent years. In this connection their side effects on the nutrient status^{1,2} and the microbiological³ make up of the soil have attracted considerable attention. However, there is some dearth of information in these fields.

Mn²⁺ exists in soil as water soluble and as exchangeable and hence in this state is available to plants. Mn⁴⁺ exists as unavailable but is reducible to available form. This element along with Fe assists in formation of chlorophyll and controls many complicated systems of oxidation reduction in plants and soils. Iron is an essential nutrient for plants. It exists as Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺. Its availability is governed by oxidation reduction potential⁴ of the soil. Along with other variables, microorganisms are specifically involved in Fe transformations.

1, 2-dibromo-3-chloropropane, commonly known as nemagon is widely used to control nematode and fungus diseases in soils. In view of the great importance of the trace elements in plant metabolism and the increasing use of pesticides for high yields of crops it was considered that an examination of the effects of halogenated pesticides, particularly nemagon, on the Fe and Mn transformations in a saline sodic soil will be useful.

Experimental

The soil used in this study (Depth, 0-30 cm) was collected from Central lowlands, type III, Aligarh Muslim University area, of Aligarh district. It was dried, crushed and sieved. The general physico-chemical properties of the soil determined and were : pH = 8.85, E.C. = 4.5×10^{-4} mhos cm⁻¹, organic matter = 0.41%, water soluble Mn = 3.2 ppm, exchangeable Mn = 8.8 ppm, reducible Mn = 73.3 ppm, exchangeable Fe = 11.9 ppm and available Fe = 38.5 ppm.

The experiments were done in earthenware pots of 20×20 cm size. They were cleaned and fitted with polythene sheets on the wall of the pots towards the inner side to prevent adsorption of water. One kilogram soil was then filled in each of the twelve pots. The samples were then treated upto the water holding capacity with distilled water. Six doses of nemagon (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 ml) were then injected into the samples at a depth of 12 cm in two replications without growing any crop. All the samples were then watered upto the water holding capacity with distilled water every week throughout the course of the experiments. Distilled water was used to avoid any contamination with impurities.

The treated samples were periodically drawn by a soil sampler at intervals of fifteen days and subjected to analysis as follows : The pH of the samples was measured in 1 : 5 soil water suspension with a pH meter with glass and calomel saturated electrode assembly. Electrical conductivity was measured with Philips conductivity meter, with dip type cell at $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ in the 1 : 5 soil water suspension. Organic matter was estimated by Walkley and Black's⁴ method using potassium dichromate, sulfuric acid and ferrous ammonium sulphate as reagents.

Water soluble, exchangeable and reducible Mn were estimated colorimetrically according to Jackson⁵ using Leeper's method as modified by Sherman and Harmer⁶ with normal ammonium acetate (pH 7) as extractant and 85% orthophosphoric acid and potassium periodate as colour reagents. For reducible Mn, 2% hydroquinone solution of normal ammonium acetate was used as extractant. The absorbance was recorded with the help of Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 at 525 nm.

Exchangeable and available Fe were determined colorimetrically by Saywell's⁷ method using normal ammonium acetate (pH 7) and normal ammonium acetate (pH 4.8) as extractants respectively ; and

hydroxylamine hydrochloride and orthophenanthroline as colour reagents. Absorbance was recorded with the help of Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 at 490 nm. Blanks were used in all cases.

The data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance according to the two way classification with one observation per cell, the null hypothesis being the equality of the effects of different doses and different time intervals. Correlation coefficients were also calculated.

Results and Discussion

Results on the effects of nemagon on the Mn and Fe status of a saline sodic soil provided interesting and consistent observations. The data on the water soluble, exchangeable, reducible and active Mn in presence of the pesticide referred to above, with different doses at various intervals of time are presented in Tables 1-4 and that for exchangeable and available Fe vide Tables 5 and 6. Each datum in the Table represents a mean of carefully recorded duplicate values.

The physico-chemical characteristics of the soil revealed that it was saline and had a distinctly alkaline reaction. This should favour oxidation transformations in Mn and Fe systems. In the studies reported here the pH showed a slight non-significant decrease (8.8 to 8.5) during nemagon treatment. No significant changes in electrical conductivity took place.

An examination of data in Table 1, showed that as compared to the control, water soluble Mn increased significantly, reached a maximum value with 0.3 ml of nemagon at 30 days and then declined. At this dose and interval of time it increased from 5.6 ppm to 10 ppm and then declined to 5.9 ppm at 90 days. The influence followed the dose order 0.3>0.4>0.2>0.5 >0.1>0.0 ml nemagon per kg of soil.

Almost similar trends but with variable intensity were observed in the case of exchangeable and active Mn (Table 2 and 4). With 0.3 ml dose of nemagon the increase in exchangeable Mn was 28.0 ppm from 8.8 ppm; and in active Mn from 73.3 to 83.6 ppm at an interval of 30 days. The influence of dose was in the order 0.3>0.2>0.4>0.1>0.5>0.0 ml nemagon per kg of soil in both the cases.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON WATER SOLUBLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg. soil	Water soluble manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	3.20	4.34	5.62	4.66	3.56	3.33	3.27	4.00
0.1	3.20	5.26	7.08	6.05	4.66	4.23	3.80	4.89
0.2	3.13	6.40	8.37	7.14	5.54	5.00	4.21	5.68
0.3	3.15	7.46	10.00	8.80	7.31	6.81	5.92	7.07
0.4	3.18	6.32	8.62	7.52	5.41	5.02	4.62	5.81
0.5	3.20	5.21	7.80	6.62	4.58	4.11	3.53	5.01
Average	3.18	5.83	7.92	6.80	5.18	4.75	4.22	

Variance ratio and L. S. D. for doses = 25.98, 0.342
 Variance ratio and L. S. D. for days = 52.01, 0.313

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON EXCHANGEABLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg soil	Exchangeable manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	8.80	14.60	16.22	14.46	12.50	11.30	10.80	12.67
0.1	8.85	15.86	17.94	16.06	14.37	13.11	12.50	14.10
0.2	8.80	20.19	23.30	20.94	18.75	17.46	16.82	18.04
0.3	8.78	25.92	28.04	25.12	22.50	20.46	18.86	21.38
0.4	8.84	21.47	22.92	21.00	20.00	18.52	17.24	18.57
0.5	8.90	16.20	18.06	16.82	15.00	13.64	12.83	14.99
Average	8.83	19.04	21.08	19.07	17.19	15.75	14.84	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for doses = 16.24, 1.320
 Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 22.08, 1.200

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON REDUCIBLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg soil	Reducible manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	61.33	56.39	55.96	55.96	58.30	58.91	59.26	57.95
0.1	61.73	55.30	53.82	54.44	55.99	56.27	57.04	56.37
0.2	61.20	53.05	49.77	50.54	52.63	53.49	53.97	53.52
0.3	61.40	47.68	45.60	46.76	47.61	49.66	51.24	49.99
0.4	61.70	50.17	48.33	48.95	49.45	50.98	52.21	51.68
0.5	61.68	54.35	51.94	52.12	54.39	55.90	57.19	55.37
Average	61.51	52.82	50.84	51.46	53.06	54.20	55.15	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for doses = 70.76, 0.672
 Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 74.06, 0.616

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON ACTIVE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg soil	Active manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	73.33	75.33	77.40	75.08	74.36	73.54	73.33	74.62
0.1	73.78	76.42	78.84	76.55	75.02	73.61	73.34	75.36
0.2	73.13	79.64	81.44	78.62	76.92	75.95	75.00	77.24
0.3	73.33	81.06	83.64	80.68	77.42	76.93	76.02	78.44
0.4	73.72	77.96	79.87	77.47	74.86	74.52	74.05	76.07
0.5	73.78	75.76	77.80	75.56	73.97	73.65	73.55	74.87
Average	73.51	77.69	79.83	77.33	75.42	74.70	74.21	

Variance ratio and L. S. D. for doses= 5.80, 1.040
 Variance ratio and L. S. D. for days=11.16, 0.950

The mechanisms by which an increase in availability of water soluble, available and active Mn occurred in fumigated and unamended soil have been variously reported by workers⁸. The very fact that all the three forms of Mn simultaneously increased and then declined showed an effect of both biological and chemical factors on the Mn status of the soil under study. Aligarh soils have been found to contain hard nodular concretions of manganiferous⁹ deposits. As the soil was wetted in presence of the fumigant, the enhanced effects of ascomycetes, actinomycetes and reinfested fungus flora: *Aspergillus niger*, the *Rhizobium*, *Thiobacillus thiooxidans* etc., resulted in a change of oxidation reduction potential of the soil system³; in the release of carboxylic acids¹⁰; and in solubilising effects. These fast ecological changes brought about a gradual increase in water soluble and available Mn²⁺ in the soil. These views were in accordance with the work of Wensley¹¹, and Martin *et al.*¹², who reported increased and highly stimulated biological activity in the soil as a result of fumigation; with the work of Klemmer¹³ who noticed that lower doses of certain eradicator type chemicals produced greater reinvasion potentials in soils; and with the results of Smith⁹ who found an increase in water soluble and available Mn²⁺ on fumigation. With the toxic effect of higher doses of the chemical on the soil microorganisms, the stimulated effect declined after a certain period, and the equilibrium shifted towards Mn⁴⁺.

The declining effect on water soluble and exchangeable Mn with passage of time was, however, due to rapid utilisation of the organic chemical as an energy source, and a shift in equilibrium between available and reducible forms of Mn caused by re-establishment of pesticide sensitive Mn oxidising bacteria such as *Bacillus*, *S. reptomyces*, *Aerobacter* etc. The view was in accordance with the observations of Charles and Paul¹⁴.

The above observations found support from the data on the correlation coefficients (Table 7). Thus while exchangeable Mn was positively correlated to water soluble form ($r=0.975$), there was a negative correlation between exchangeable and reducible Mn ($r=-0.979$).

The results on the exchangeable and available Fe provided an interesting correlation between Fe and Mn status of the soil. Thus as in the case of Mn, exchangeable and available Fe (Tables 5 and 6) significantly increased, reached a maximum value with 0.3 ml dose of nemagon at 30 days of its application and then significantly declined. The effect of dose on the increase was in the order $0.3 > 0.2 > 0.4 > 0.1 > 0.5 > 0.0$ ml nemagon per kg soil in case of exchangeable Fe, and $0.3 > 0.4 > 0.2 > 0.5 > 0.1 > 0.0$ in case of available Fe. The maximum increase was 24.2 ppm from 11.9 ppm in case of exchangeable Fe (Table 5) and 57.5 from 38.4 ppm in case of available Fe (Table 6).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON EXCHANGEABLE IRON OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg soil	Exchangeable iron in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	11.90	14.32	15.60	14.00	12.88	12.14	12.00	13.26
0.1	12.00	17.24	19.54	17.08	15.79	15.00	14.21	15.82
0.2	12.02	19.78	22.08	19.00	17.15	16.43	15.72	17.45
0.3	11.87	21.88	24.19	21.62	20.00	19.28	18.72	19.65
0.4	12.11	18.94	20.08	17.98	16.43	15.71	15.00	16.58
0.5	11.90	16.88	19.12	15.76	14.28	13.56	12.86	13.94
Average	11.97	18.17	20.10	17.57	16.07	15.35	14.75	

Variance ratio and L. S. D. for doses=33.52, 0.559
 Variance ratio and L. S. D. for days=40.73, 0.612

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON AVAILABLE IRON OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Dose in ml per kg soil	Available iron in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.0	38.40	45.09	48.20	45.04	43.02	41.64	40.41	43.12
0.1	38.56	47.92	50.84	46.96	44.24	42.60	41.50	44.66
0.2	38.60	50.22	53.52	49.96	46.96	44.86	43.32	46.78
0.3	38.40	54.26	57.46	53.86	50.74	48.86	47.72	50.19
0.4	38.42	52.26	55.39	51.74	49.68	47.22	46.00	48.67
0.5	38.36	50.16	53.32	49.86	46.94	45.72	44.51	46.98
Average	38.46	49.99	53.12	49.57	46.93	45.15	43.93	

Variance ratio and L. S. D. for doses = 29.89, 0.782
 Variance ratio and L. S. D. for days = 89.98, 0.717

TABLE 7—CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS BETWEEN DIFFERENT FORMS OF MANGANESE AND IRON

Sl. No.	Form	Water soluble Mn	Reducible Mn	Exchangeable Fe	Available Fe
1.	Exchangeable Mn ²⁺	+0.975	-0.979	+0.942	+0.920
2.	Water soluble Mn ²⁺	—	-0.967	+0.969	+0.948
3.	Reducible Mn ⁴⁺	—	—	-0.928	-0.925
4.	Exchangeable Fe ²⁺	—	—	—	+0.848

An examination of the correlation coefficients (Table 7) further showed that there existed significant positive correlations between exchangeable Mn and exchangeable and available Fe ($r=0.942$ and 0.920 respectively) as well as between water soluble Mn and exchangeable and available Fe ($r=0.969$ and 0.948 respectively). A positive correlation was also observed between the two forms of Fe ($r=0.848$). The two forms of Fe were, however, negatively and significantly correlated to reducible Mn ($r=-0.928$ and -0.925 respectively).

The above observations pointed to the fact that conditions affecting Fe and Mn availability in soils were almost similar, a view in accordance with the results of Smith⁹. The reducible character of organic matter in soil and its microbial decomposition with liberation of acids, the drop in oxidation-reduction potential in moist conditions of the soil, stimulation in the activity of micro-organism by the pesticides extending upto a period of about 4 weeks and a favourable¹⁵ pH, all contributed towards an increase in exchangeable and available Fe. With dissipation of the organic chemical, the stimulatory effects declined; and with Fe bacteria⁸ taking over, both the forms of Fe suffered a declining effect after a period of 30 days. The results were in agreement with the observations of Pringsheim^{16,17} and Alexander⁸.

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